

21st CENTURY LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF SCHOOL HEADS AND PUBLIC ELEMENTARY TEACHERS' COMPETENCY IN CLUSTER 7 CALAMBA CITY

Kheycil B. Estrañero, LPT, MAEd

Bunggo Elementary School, Schools Division of Calamba City, Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15532590>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the level of 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads and identified their relationship with public elementary teachers' competency within the Cluster 7 Division of Calamba City. Drawing on the principles outlined by Maxwell, the study assessed the level to which these 21st-century leadership qualities were manifested by school heads. Furthermore, the research investigated the correlation between the manifestations of 21st-century leadership qualities and the teachers' competency framework. The findings showed that school heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibited a high level of manifestation in the defined leadership qualities proposed by Maxwell. Moreover, a positive correlation was identified between the manifestations of these leadership qualities and the teachers' competency. The probability values were .000, which is less than the significance at .05 thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. The values lie between 0.41 to 0.75, then it was said to have a moderate small to high positive correlation. These results highlighted the significance of 21st-century leadership qualities in enhancing teachers' performance. A leadership program was proposed to improve leadership qualities demonstrated by the school heads that may not be prominently displayed, thereby making a valuable contribution to teachers' competence. The leadership program is called "I-LEAD: Embracing the 21st Century Leadership qualities." This study provided useful insights for educational institutions and policymakers looking to increase teachers' competence through leadership development programs, while also adding to the body of knowledge already available on educational leadership.

Keywords: *21st century leadership qualities, teachers' competency framework, leadership program*

INTRODUCTION

Leadership covers the capacity to guide, encourage, and inspire a group of others toward the accomplishment of shared aims or objectives. A leader is someone who assumes responsibility, gives instructions, and inspires others to collaborate productively. To lead a group of people or an organization, a person possesses a variety of abilities, characteristics, and attitudes.

Educational leadership has been essential and had a big impact on how well learning environments work, how well teachers develop professionally, and how successful educational institutions are. A wide range of actions targeted at promoting constructive change and enhancement in the educational system were included in educational leadership, which went beyond administrative positions. It was necessary to build an adaptable and dynamic educational system that equipped pupils to succeed in the 21st century (Culduz, 2023).

According to Sutherland et al. (2013, as quoted in Arrieta, 2020), the Philippines has a rich history that shaped education and policy in a multicultural setting, which impacted the growth and application of school leadership. The fundamental Filipino ideals of community and kinship are tested by periods of Spanish and American colonization, which also affected the way that contemporary school leadership development and training occurred in the Philippines. The importance of kinship dynamics in the Filipino concept of self and social relationships further defines the function of school leaders in the nation. Kinship is the basis of social organization in the Philippines, spanning from native communities to the elite ethnic and social groups of colonial times.

The effectiveness of managerial styles of leadership and management practices determines how well the organization achieves its objectives. Effective leadership is essential for businesses of all sizes to thrive, and companies led by effective leaders typically innovate, adapt to shifting markets and environments, find innovative solutions to problems, and continue to operate at a high level. On the other hand, the organization's capacity to carry out and integrate strategic objectives is severely impacted by ineffective leadership.

On the other hand, the term "competencies" describes a set of abilities, information, conduct, and qualities that facilitate more efficient or superior work output. Given that teaching was a challenging profession, teachers used a variety of talents to address the evolving landscape of education. Teacher Competency is a set of skills, attitudes, personal characteristics, and abilities that enable the teacher to act professionally and appropriately in a situation.

According to Fauth (2019), students' interest in their studies was favorably correlated with various aspects of teacher competence, including pedagogical topic understanding, self-efficacy, and instructional enthusiasm. When teachers demonstrated a deep understanding of the subjects they taught, believed in their ability to teach effectively, and showed excitement in their instruction, students were more

likely to be interested in their learning. Additionally, student achievement was positively correlated with teacher self-efficacy. This means that when teachers have confidence in their teaching abilities, it not only improves their performance but also significantly enhances their students' academic success. This positive relationship between teacher competence and student outcomes underscores the importance of investing in teacher development and support to promote both student engagement and achievement.

Moreover, the study by Istiqomah et al. (2019) emphasized that initiatives to improve teacher competency were essential for raising educational standards and increasing student achievement. By investing in the professional development and advancement of educators, governments and educational institutions demonstrated their dedication to delivering high-quality instruction, encouraging student success, and creating a better future for future generations.

Furthermore, as stated by Shidiq et al. (2022), most target groups focused on strengthening preservice teachers' competencies, and teacher preparation generated the greatest number of initiatives for improving the capacities of teacher education. Further domains of teacher education strategies that were highlighted by multiple researchers were also identified. These domains included classroom practice transformation, increased student accomplishment, pedagogical content knowledge, subject knowledge in terms of knowledge and communication skills, interpersonal skills, and outcome-based instructional design skills.

Teaching in Southeast Asia offers a unique challenge, with significant differences in teacher preparation and skill levels among countries. Students' well-being has to take primacy, necessitating an all-encompassing system that measures requirements for teachers and allows them to be consistent in their educational output. As a result, the Teacher Competency Framework is created as a thorough reference outlining the basic knowledge and skills needed for effective teaching. This not only meets the demands of distinct countries but also provides unifying objectives that comply with the Professional Standard for Teachers in the Philippines. This study is the result of a regional partnership with eleven Southeast Asian Ministries of Education. A framework to enhance education is being developed by ten (10) ASEAN nations plus Timor-Leste.

This study assessed the qualities of school leaders and the outcomes of teachers' competency, focusing on the connection between 21st-century leadership qualities and teacher competencies in Cluster 7 Calamba City to prove that leadership can make teachers teach better. It is with sincere intention that the teacher researcher conducted this study without any prejudice on the part of the heads of the schools and teachers in Cluster 7 Calamba City to provide a report on the status of the manifestation of the leadership qualities and teachers' competency.

This study was based on John Maxwell's 21 Indispensable Leadership Qualities. According to Maxwell (2019), there were identified, cultivated, and refined personal attributes that a person must have to become an effective leader, the type of leader that people desire to follow. Character, charisma, commitment, communication, competence, courage, discernment, focus, generosity, initiative, passion, positive

attitude, problem-solving, relationships, responsibility, security, self-discipline, servanthood, teachability, and vision were among these qualities. A leader who exhibited this set of qualities would be effective in his/her leadership positions.

Another theoretical foundation for this study was the Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework (SEA-TCF), which supported teachers to improve their performance to bring about quality education for all students in Southeast Asia. SEA-TCF consisted of four essential competencies: knowing and understanding what to teach, helping students learn, engaging in the community, and becoming a better teacher every day. Teachers with high skill levels became role models and advocates of educational progress. Through their excellence, they became more effective guides and leaders in delivering high-quality education to their students.

According to Mhunpiew and Asavisanu (2023), This study's importance lies in its capacity to let educators understand their own proficiencies and cultivate the skills required for the growth and learning of students. As such, the school the SEA-TCF could be used by administrators for the teacher professional development program. Additionally, high-competency teachers are beneficial to their students. Instructors are crucial in aiding.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the extent of 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads and public elementary teachers' competency in cluster 7 Calamba City. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves in terms of:

- 1.1 Character,
- 1.2 Charisma,
- 1.3 Commitment,
- 1.4 Communication,
- 1.5 Competence,
- 1.6 Courage,
- 1.7 Discernment,
- 1.8 Focus,
- 1.9 Generosity,
- 1.10 Initiative,
- 1.11 Listening,
- 1.12 Passion,
- 1.13 Positive Attitude,
- 1.14 Problem Solving,
- 1.15 Relationships,
- 1.16 Responsibility,
- 1.17 Security,
- 1.18 Self-Discipline,
- 1.19 Servanthood,

1.20 Teachability and,
1.21 Vision?

2. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the school heads and teachers on the level of manifestation of 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads?

3. What is the level of competency of public elementary teachers in Cluster 7 Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers in terms of:

3.1 Knowing and Understanding What to Teach,

3.2 Helping Students Learn,

3.3 Engaging the Community,

3.4 Becoming a Better Teacher Every Day?

4. Is there a significant difference between the assessment of the school head and teacher on the level of teachers' competency?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 Calamba City?

6. Based on the findings of the study, what leadership program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed quantitative research design. According to Leavy (2022), quantitative research emphasizes the importance of accurate measurement, control, objectivity, generalizability, breadth, statistical descriptions, and explanatory power. By providing relevant data on relationships and causal relationships, this method improved knowledge in several different domains.

Furthermore, as defined by Yazon et al. (2019), descriptive correlational research included obtaining primary data regarding the current circumstances and determining how two highly relevant variables were related to one another. This method described the characteristics and/or behavior of the sample population and examined the manifestation level of 21st-century leadership qualities, the teachers' competency level, and the relationship between these leadership qualities and teachers' competency among public elementary teachers in Cluster 7 Division of Calamba City.

According to Creswell and Hirose (2019), researchers employed correlational research designs to quantify and characterize the strength of the correlation between two or more variables or score sets. This method involved measuring the subjects' scores on two variables, with no other variables changed, to determine if there was a relationship. The relationship between two or more non-manipulated variables was investigated through correlational research.

As mentioned in Gonzales (2022), descriptive correlational research aimed to

describe the relationships between variables rather than determine cause-and-effect relationship. Specifically, this study determined the significant relationship between the manifestation level of leadership qualities and teachers' competency level among public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Division of Calamba City.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1.1

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Character

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
Honesty Places great importance on honesty and always strives to be truthful and sincere in his/her words and actions.	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Integrity Values on adhering to moral and ethical principles in behavior.	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Diligence Makes his/her team members inspired, makes sure that projects are completed on time and to a high standard, and agents to create a culture of hard work and dedication within the organization.	3.83	FM	3.75	FM	3.79	FM
Accountability Makes himself/herself responsible of his/her decisions or actions and the outcomes whether a success or failure.	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Ethics Promotes and maintain strong moral principles that guide behavior and decision-making, based on values such as fairness, justice, and respect.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
General Assessment	3.97	FM	3.79	FM	3.88	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Character was Fully Manifested (3.88). “The school head promotes and maintains strong moral principles that guide behavior and decision-making, based on values such as fairness, justice, and respect” which yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91** and was interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. On the other hand, “the school head Makes his/her team members inspired, makes sure that projects are completed on time and to a high standard, and agents to create a culture of hard work and dedication within the organization” received the lowest composite mean score of responses with **3.79** and interpreted as **Fully Manifested**.

School heads in public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of character. The school head serves as the cornerstone for developing a moral, welcoming, and supportive learning environment that supports kids' overall development and gets them ready for a purposeful and accountable life after school. However, it is suggested that additional focus should be given to improving to inspiring the team to complete projects on time and to a high standard, and agents to create a culture of hard work and dedication within the organization.

As stated by Subedi (2023), school heads of community schools led and managed schools through the development of innovative projects and programs creating

an engaged learning environment at school. A visionary school leader had a dream of creating an engaged learning environment at school, for which unwavering determination seemed to be a must. They were found focused on their task with full commitment and dedication.

Table 1.2

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Charisma

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Influence exhibits high sense of ability to persuade, influence and inspire others towards achieving specific goal.	4.00	FM	3.72	FM	3.86	FM
Inspiration has a talent for stimulating or arousing creative, intellectual, or emotional thought or action.	3.83	FM	3.69	FM	3.76	FM
Positivity embodies a quality of being optimistic, hopeful, and constructive.	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Enthusiasm exhibits positive and energetic attitude toward a particular task or goal.	4.00	FM	3.73	FM	3.87	FM
Confidence strongly believes in his/her capabilities, attributes, and judgment	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
General Assessment	3.97	FM	3.74	FM	3.86	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Charisma was Fully Manifested (**3.86**) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicators “The school head embodies a quality of being optimistic, hopeful, and constructive and exhibits a positive and energetic attitude toward a particular task or goal” and “the school head strongly believes in his/her capabilities, attributes, and judgment” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.90**. On the other hand, “the school head has a talent for stimulating or arousing creative, intellectual, or emotional thought or action” received the lowest composite mean score of responses with **3.76**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of charisma. They demonstrate optimism, self-assurance, and a constructive approach toward their colleagues and pupils. They are characterized by confidence, resilience, collaboration, and trust. Their leadership style contributes to a supportive learning environment where everyone feels inspired to strive for excellence and achieve their full potential. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given to enhance their capacity to encourage intellectual and emotional growth and creativity participation. It also implies that even with the exceptional charm and leadership of the leaders’ abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering an environment that inspires creativity and encourages a higher degree of intellectual and

emotional involvement in the school community.

According to the results of Brown and Nwagbara (2021), applying a style of leadership that combines transformational leadership, intellectual intelligence, and emotional intelligence, referred to as "leading with the heart," can help to foster the growth of a certain type of leadership in organizations.

Table 1.3

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Commitment

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Dedication demonstrates a strong commitment and effort given to a task, goal, or cause	3.83	FM	3.77	FM	3.80	FM
Persistence exhibits a determination to keep going despite obstacles or difficulties.	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Work ethic. maintains a set of moral values that inspires people to put dedication and high level of quality to work.	3.83	FM	3.74	FM	3.79	FM
Loyalty creates an environment where the community feels allegiance, faithfulness, and devotion.	3.83	FM	3.78	FM	3.81	FM
Determination exhibits a firmness of purpose and resolve to achieve a goal or overcome a challenge.	4.00	FM	3.75	FM	3.88	FM
General Assessment	3.88	FM	3.77	FM	3.83	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Commitment was Fully Manifested (3.83) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head exhibits a determination to keep going despite obstacles or difficulties” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.90**. On the other hand, the indicator “the school head maintains a set of moral values that inspires people to put dedication and high level of quality to work” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.79**.

School heads in public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of commitment. They exhibit a determination to keep going despite obstacles or difficulties. This leadership quality contributes to a culture of perseverance, optimism, and achievement within the school community, ultimately leading to greater success and fulfillment. However, there is an opportunity for further improvement in maintaining a set of moral values that inspires people to put dedication and a high level of quality to work.

Villirilli (2021) stressed out that those surrounding a leader can be motivated to act morally by them. Others will follow your lead and behave ethically if you lead by example. By giving them a set of behaviors to follow for the larger good, moral leaders can thereby have a positive impact on many people.

Table 1.4

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Communication

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
The school head ...						
Listening Skills						
gives full attention to someone is saying and understand the speaker's perspective and needs.	4.00	FM	3.77	FM	3.89	FM
Clarity						
values the quality of being easily understood and expressed.	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Articulation						
values the clear and precise pronunciation and enunciation of words.	3.50	FM	3.75	FM	3.63	FM
Persuasion						
convinces or influences someone to believe or do something.	3.83	FM	3.75	FM	3.79	FM
Non-verbal Cues						
gives recognition and value to non-verbal cues, such as gestures, facial expressions, and body language in communication	3.67	FM	3.71	FM	3.69	FM
General Assessment	3.80	FM	3.75	FM	3.78	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Communication was Fully Manifested (3.78) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head gives full attention to what someone is saying and understands the speaker’s perspective and needs” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.89**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head values the clear and precise pronunciation and enunciation of words” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.63**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of communication. They give full attention to what someone is saying and understand the speaker’s perspective and needs. It fosters trust, collaboration, empowerment, problem-solving, and empathetic leadership within the school community. This quality of attentive listening contributes to a positive and supportive school culture where everyone feels valued, respected, and heard.

However, according to Alfari (2024), there has been an opportunity for further improvement in the school heads' clear and precise pronunciation and enunciation of words. Clear and precise pronunciation and enunciation were crucial for school heads to effectively communicate, serve as role models, enhance comprehension, demonstrate professionalism and credibility, promote inclusivity and accessibility, maintain effective

leadership presence, and cultivate a positive school culture. Investing in communication skills development could further strengthen the leadership effectiveness and impact of school heads within their respective communities.

According to Rajab (2021), effective communication has been crucial to productivity at work. If a leadership directive or policy was not adequately conveyed in advance, it negatively affected the productivity of the workforce. Information could be given to or received from other parties through communication, which was a crucial tool. It was possible to say that effective communication within a firm determined whether goals could be accomplished; with effective communication, there was reciprocal interaction from every employee in the form of directives, recommendations, opinions, and criticisms.

Table 1.5

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Competence

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Knowledge <i>gives value to knowledge, information, concepts, and ideas.</i>	4.00	FM	3.77	FM	3.89	FM
Expertise <i>specializes in a specific skill or field.</i>	3.83	FM	3.72	FM	3.78	FM
Skills <i>gives recognition to the importance of skills.</i>	4.00	FM	3.74	FM	3.87	FM
Experience <i>gives value to values experience.</i>	4.00	FM	3.78	FM	3.89	FM
Continuous Learning <i>recognizes the importance of continuous learning.</i>	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
General Assessment	3.97	FM	3.76	FM	3.87	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Competence was Fully Manifested (3.87) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head recognizes the importance of continuous learning” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.90**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head specializes in a specific skill or field” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.78**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of competence. They recognize the importance of continuous learning. It is essential for school heads as it fosters adaptability, promotes professional growth, stimulates innovation, enhances decision-making, models lifelong learning, enables effective leadership, and improves student outcomes. By prioritizing continuous learning, school heads can lead their schools with vision, resilience, and excellence in a dynamic educational landscape. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given to enhancing their specific skill or field. It also implies that there is always room for

development in terms of fostering innovation and driving positive outcomes for students, teachers, and the broader school community.

According to Vasquez (2022), an excellent school leader would continually seek out new methods to advance, acquire new abilities, and hone the ones they already possess. Leaders could adapt to changing needs, promote innovation and creativity, enhance leadership effectiveness, empower staff and students, respond to stakeholder needs, and drive continuous improvement within their schools.

Table 1.6

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Courage

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Bravery practices bravery, courage, and strength to face fear, danger, or uncertainty.	3.83	FM	3.75	FM	3.79	FM
Resilience gives value to resilience.	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Risk-taking gives recognition to the value of risk-taking.	3.67	FM	3.73	FM	3.70	FM
Adaptability gives value to adaptability.	4.00	FM	3.78	FM	3.89	FM
Assertiveness promotes assertiveness.	3.83	FM	3.74	FM	3.79	FM
General Assessment	3.87	FM	3.75	FM	3.81	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Courage was Fully Manifested (3.81) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head gives value to adaptability” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.89**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head gives recognition to the value of risk-taking” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.70**.

It can be inferred that school heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestation of courage. They give value to adaptability. It enables their schools to navigate change successfully, respond to emerging challenges, embrace innovation and creativity, promote flexibility and resilience, model a growth mindset, enhance communication and collaboration, and drive organizational agility.

By prioritizing adaptability, school leaders ensure that schools are well-equipped to thrive in an ever-changing world. On the other hand, it is advised that additional consideration should be given to the importance of recognizing the value of risk-taking. It also implies that there is always room for development in terms of contributing to a culture

of innovation, resilience, creativity, and continuous improvement within the school community. They empower individuals to embrace challenges, learn from experiences, and contribute meaningfully to the growth and success of the school.

According to Robb (2020), the school heads had a crucial role in establishing the school's culture and equipping pupils for today's difficulties. It highlighted the value of leadership in creating an atmosphere where creativity and innovation could thrive and highlighted the need for educators as a group to embrace risk-taking and adjust to the ever-changing needs of the modern world.

Table 1.7

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Discernment

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Judgment provides informed decisions that are based on evaluations, reasons, and experience.	3.83	FM	3.75	FM	3.79	FM
Insight has the ability to decipher the true nature of things, situations, and people. .	3.83	FM	3.70	FM	3.77	FM
Wisdom capable of making decisions based on deep understanding and application of knowledge.	3.67	FM	3.71	FM	3.69	FM
Intuition instinctively understands something without the need for conscious reasoning.	4.00	FM	3.72	FM	3.86	FM
Perceptiveness can notice and understand not so obvious details, emotions, or thoughts.	3.83	FM	3.72	FM	3.78	FM
General Assessment	3.83	FM	3.72	FM	3.78	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Discernment was Fully Manifested (3.78) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head instinctively understands something without the need for conscious reasoning” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.86**. On the other hand, the indicator “the school head capable of making decisions based on deep understanding and application of knowledge” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.69**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of discernment. They instinctively understand something without the need for conscious reasoning. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be

given to enhancing their capability of making decisions based on deep understanding and application of knowledge. It also implies that even with good judgment and leadership of the leaders' abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering an educational environment that prioritizes student success, utilizes resources effectively, fosters a positive school culture, and adapts to evolving needs and challenges in education.

As stated by Hermans (2021), leaders who "changed and motivated people to perform above expectations while transcending self-interest for the welfare of the organization" were described as transformational leaders. Decision-making that was focused on the future (educational goals), influenced by the character traits of leaders (purity of heart), and that emphasized teleological ethics as a foundational principle was known as discernment.

Table 1.8

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Focus

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Concentration						
focuses his/her attention and mental effort on a task or objective.	4.00	FM	3.70	FM	3.85	FM
Attention						
focuses his/her mind on something, being present and engaged.	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Prioritization						
determines the relative importance or urgency of tasks or goals. .	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Organization						
arranges and plans tasks, responsibilities, and resources efficiently and effectively to achieve a goal.	3.83	FM	3.74	FM	3.79	FM
Time Management						
gives an efficient time management to prioritize tasks and complete them within the given time frame.	3.67	FM	3.75	FM	3.71	FM
General Assessment	3.87	FM	3.74	FM	3.81	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Focus was Fully Manifested (3.81) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head determines the relative importance or urgency of tasks or goals” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.88**. On the other hand, the indicator “the school head gives an efficient time management to prioritize tasks and complete them within the given time frame” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.71**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit a strong manifestation of focus. They determine the relative importance or urgency of tasks

or goals. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given to enhancing their efficient time management to prioritize tasks and complete them within the given time frame. However, there may be opportunities to further enhance their ability to arrange and plan tasks, responsibilities, and resources efficiently and effectively. There is always room for development in terms of efficient time management, maintaining productivity, meeting deadlines, making strategic decisions, balancing responsibilities, modeling positive behavior, handling challenges effectively, and promoting personal well-being.

As stated by Castelhana (2023), acquiring successful time management abilities was crucial for success in all facets of life, particularly leadership. Leaders might accomplish goals, lower their stress levels, and increase productivity by prioritizing their work, making clear goals, and using their time wisely.

Table 1.9

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Generosity

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Kindness exhibits genuine concern, compassion, empathy, and respect to others.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
Compassion feels for others' feelings, sufferings and pain and exhibits the willingness to alleviate their pain.	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Liberality generous in sharing his/her time, knowledge, and resources with others, without the expectation to receive the same back.	3.83	FM	3.80	FM	3.82	FM
Empathy shows understanding to what others feel and need.	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Service is pro-active in helping others and contributes to the betterment of the community.	4.00	FM	3.82	FM	3.91	FM
General Assessment	3.97	FM	3.80	FM	3.89	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Generosity was Fully Manifested (3.89) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicators “The school head exhibits genuine concern, compassion, empathy, and respect to others” and “The school head is proactive in helping others and contributes to the betterment of the community” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head generous in sharing his/her time, knowledge, and resources with others, without the expectation to receive the same back” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.82**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of generosity. They exhibit genuine concern, compassion, empathy, and respect for others and are proactive in helping others and contributing to the betterment of the community. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given to generous in sharing his/her time, knowledge, and resources with others, without the expectation to receive the same back. It also implies that even with the genuine leadership of the leaders' abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering collaboration, empowering others, leading by example, and creating a learning culture.

In another study by Beck (2012, as cited in Loughran, 2021), it was mentioned that the principle of generosity that Aristotle outlined was still relevant to effective leadership techniques today. Generosity, the virtue of sharing valuable things with others, was essential in this context because they were connected to the most fundamental leadership skills as it was essential to the growth of all social and political institutions, including educational institutions.

Table 1.10

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Initiative

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
Creativity comes up with ideas that are innovative ideas to improve the school and improve student learning experiences.	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Ingenuity practices resourcefulness, inventiveness, and cleverness in finding the best solutions to the problems of the school community.	3.83	FM	3.74	FM	3.79	FM
Proactivity initiates and anticipates the possible problems and take the necessary actions to prevent or exploit them.	3.83	FM	3.75	FM	3.79	FM
Ambition is very determined to achieve success and reach his/her goals and aspirations. .	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Self-motivation can motivate own self without the help of external factors and can continue amidst challenges. .	3.83	FM	3.78	FM	3.81	FM
General Assessment	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Initiative was Fully Manifested (3.80) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head can motivate own self without the help of external factors and can continue amidst challenges” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.81**. On the other hand, the indicators “The school head practices resourcefulness, inventiveness, and cleverness in finding the best solutions to the problems of the school community” and “the school head

initiates and anticipates the possible problems and take the necessary actions to prevent or exploit them” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.79**.

The level of manifestations of school heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibits a strong manifestation of initiative. They have a proactive leadership style, as seen by their demonstrated self-motivation and ability to see issues or opportunities arising. They actively pursue achievement and assume leadership responsibilities in their positions.

However, there are opportunities for further development in terms of sharpening their originality, resourcefulness, and cunning in coming up with fresh approaches and strategies to problems. This implication suggests that while the school heads possess commendable initiative and leadership qualities, they can benefit from nurturing their creative problem-solving skills. These leaders may better prepare themselves to handle complex challenges and adapt to an ever-changing educational environment by developing an environment that supports innovative thinking, resourcefulness, and a willingness to explore new ideas. Emphasizing and cultivating these traits can assist them in dealing with challenges more successfully, which will eventually result in a more productive learning environment.

Buffone (2021) argued a leader's intelligence is crucial for future leadership since it depends on their capacity to regularly connect with all the different aspects of their surroundings, particularly in the rapidly changing educational situation. Leaders needed to demonstrate resourcefulness, creativity, and astuteness.

Table 1.11

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Listening

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
The school head ...						
Active Listening pays attention to someone who is talking and provides relevant response.	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Empathy recognizes the feelings, needs and emotion of others.	4.00	FM	3.75	FM	3.88	FM
Transparency provides an open, honest, and clear communication and decision-making to the school community.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
Responsiveness provides solution to the needs of the community in a timely manner.	4.00	FM	3.74	FM	3.87	FM
Feedback can provide feedback and openly receives feedback from others.	4.00	FM	3.75	FM	3.88	FM
General Assessment	4.00	FM	3.77	FM	3.89	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Listening was Fully Manifested (3.89) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head provides an open, honest, and clear communication and decision-making to the school community” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head provides a solution to the needs of the community in a timely manner” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.87**.

It can be inferred that school heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of listening. They provide open, honest, and clear communication and decision-making to the school community. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given to provide solutions to the needs of the community promptly. It also implies that even with good listening and leadership of the leaders’ abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering building trust, enhancing communication, addressing urgent matters, preventing escalation, supporting continuous improvement, demonstrating leadership competence, promoting engagement and satisfaction, and meeting expectations.

According to the results of Kluger and Itzchakov (2021), listening has been linked with and may even be the foundation of many organizational outcomes, such as those that were associated with leadership, well-being, relationship quality (such as trust), understanding, and mindsets at work, and job performance.

Table 1.12

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Passion

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
Vitality exhibits a dynamic, proactive and a strong sense of purpose and direction for the school.	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Dedication commits to completing tasks to the best of his/her ability and strives for excellence.	3.83	FM	3.77	FM	3.80	FM
Inspiration provides inspiration to others to achieve their goals and aspirations.	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Motivation pushes people to act and achieve goals.	4.00	FM	3.74	FM	3.87	FM
Purpose exhibits a clear sense of direction and meaning in life and aligns his/her actions with this sense of purpose. Promotes and maintain strong moral principles that guide behavior and decision-making, based on values such as fairness, justice, and respect.	4.00	FM	3.75	FM	3.88	FM
General Assessment	3.93	FM	3.76	FM	3.85	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Passion was Fully Manifested (3.89) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicators “The school head provides inspiration to others to achieve their goals and aspirations” and “The school head exhibits a clear sense of direction and meaning in life and aligns his/her actions with this sense of purpose. Promotes and maintain strong moral principles that guide behavior and decision-making, based on values such as fairness, justice, and respect” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.88**. On the other hand, the indicators “the school head exhibits a dynamic, proactive and a strong sense of purpose and direction for the school” and “the school head commits to completing tasks to the best of his/her ability and strives for excellence” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.80**.

School heads of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of passion. They inspire others to achieve their goals and aspirations. They exhibit a clear sense of direction and meaning in life and align his/her actions with this sense of purpose. They promote and maintain strong moral principles that guide behavior and decision-making, based on values such as fairness, justice, and respect. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given to their dynamic, proactive, and strong sense of purpose and direction for the school and commit to completing tasks to the best of their ability and striving for excellence”. It also implies that even with dedication and leadership of the leaders’ abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering a strong sense of purpose and a commitment to excellence plays a pivotal role in driving vision, fostering innovation, creating a positive culture, promoting accountability, supporting continuous improvement, and building trust within the school community. These qualities contribute significantly to the overall success and effectiveness of the school's leadership and operations.

As stated by Trivissono (2020), a strong desire to engage in leadership that one appreciates, values, and regularly devotes time and energy to, and that was an integral part of one's identity was known as a passion for leadership.

Table 1.13

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Positive Attitude

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
Optimism <i>possesses a positive outlook and attitude towards life and the future.</i>	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Resilience <i>is capable of recovering gracefully from numerous setbacks. .</i>	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Confidence <i>has self-confidence and believes in his/her abilities.</i>	3.83	FM	3.80	FM	3.82	FM
Enthusiasm <i>is positive towards the tasks and challenges that come with them.</i>	4.00	FM	3.78	FM	3.89	FM

Hopefulness

<i>is hopeful for positive outcome and brighter future.</i>	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
General Assessment	3.93	FM	3.79	FM	3.86	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Positive Attitude was Fully Manifested (3.86) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head is hopeful for a positive outcome and brighter future” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head is capable of recovering gracefully from numerous setbacks” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.80**.

School heads of public elementary schools of cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit a strong manifestation of a positive attitude. Their dedication to leadership is clear evidence of their optimistic outlook, belief in favorable results, and confidence in themselves. However, there are options for enhancing their resiliency and capacity to overcome setbacks. This suggests that while the school heads demonstrate commendable positivity and leadership qualities, they can benefit from developing greater resilience in the face of challenges.

Smith et al. (2022) highlighted the significance of resilience in various leadership contexts, emphasizing its positive impact on work outcomes for both individuals and organizations. This included improved work performance, increased job engagement, enhanced well-being, and the development of stronger leadership capabilities. Leaders can enhance their resilience by acquiring effective coping skills and cultivating a more positive mindset towards challenges. By adopting resilient attitudes, characterized by a paradoxical perspective on challenges, leaders can effectively adapt to difficulties and adversities, ultimately resulting in favorable outcomes.

Table 1.14

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Problem Solving

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
Analytical Skills draws logical conclusion based on the analysis and interpretation of information.	3.83	FM	3.71	FM	3.77	FM
Critical Thinking provides evaluation and analysis of information objectively and logically.	3.67	FM	3.74	FM	3.71	FM
Originality exhibits willingness to explore new ideas and approaches, and to challenge conventional thinking.	4.00	FM	3.74	FM	3.87	FM

Creativity

is imaginative to provide original ideas to develop new solutions, products, or concepts.

4.00 FM 3.72 FM 3.86 FM

Decision-making

provides decisions that are effective and timely based on the available information.

4.00 FM 3.77 FM 3.89 FM

General Assessment

3.90 FM 3.73 FM 3.82 FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Problem-solving was Fully Manifested (3.82) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head provides decisions that are effective and timely based on the available information yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.89**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head provides evaluation and analysis of information objectively and logically” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.71**.

School heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of problem-solving. They provide decisions that are effective and timely based on the available information. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given in providing evaluation and analysis of information objectively and logically. It also implies that even with high critical thinking and leadership of the leaders’ abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering decision-making, accuracy, fairness, strategic planning, accountability, problem-solving, professionalism, and credibility. These qualities contribute to effective leadership and the overall success of the school in achieving its educational goals.

As stated in the book Leadership-problem Solving Skills by Rowinski (2023), one of the key attributes of a great leader is their ability to effectively solve problems. A leader with strong problem-solving skills could identify and analyze problems, generate potential solutions, and make decisions that could lead to positive outcomes.

Table 1.15

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Relationship

Indicators	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
The school head ...						
Collaboration and I act together towards a common goal and share responsibilities, ideas, and resources.	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Teamwork manifests cooperation and collaboration in effective manner to achieve a common goal.	4.00	FM	3.75	FM	3.88	FM
Networking	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM

creates and sustains relationships with others to share information, resources, and opportunities.

Trust-building

builds and maintains trust with others by being reliable, honest, and transparent in interactions.

4.00 FM 3.78 FM 3.89 FM

Interpersonal Skills

communicates effectively with others by actively listening and showing empathy and provides conflict resolution.

4.00 FM 3.79 FM 3.90 FM

General Assessment 4.00 FM 3.77 FM 3.89 FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Relationship was Fully Manifested (3.89) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head and I act together towards a common goal and share responsibilities, ideas, and resources” and “The school head communicates effectively with others by actively listening and showing empathy and provides conflict resolution” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.90**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head manifests cooperation and collaboration effectively to achieve a common goal” and “the school head creates and sustains relationships with others to share information, resources, and opportunities” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.88**.

School heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong manifestations of relationship. They act together towards a common goal and share responsibilities, ideas, and resources. They communicate effectively with others by actively listening showing empathy and providing conflict resolution. Nonetheless, it is advised that additional consideration be given importance on cooperation and collaboration effectively to achieve a common goal and create and sustain relationships with others to share information, resources, and opportunities. It also implies that even with good relationships and leadership of the leaders’ abilities, there is always room for development in terms of fostering cooperation, collaboration, and relationship-building. These qualities not only benefit the school's overall effectiveness but also contribute to a positive and supportive educational experience for everyone involved.

According to Pearce et al. (2003, as cited in Larson, 2020), the efficiency of living systems of relationships did not depend on a single, hero leader, but rather on the leadership practices that were ingrained in a system of interdependencies at many levels inside the business, according to new models of leadership. This ushered in a new era of shared leadership, also known as "post-heroic" leadership, which was a novel strategy meant to alter organizational practices, structures, and working relationships. In new theories, leadership was viewed as a more relational process, a shared or dispersed phenomenon that occurs at various levels and has been reliant on social connections and influence networks.

Table 1.16

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Responsibility

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
Liability is responsible and makes himself/herself accountable for his/her behavior, even in challenging circumstances.	3.83	FM	3.79	FM	3.81	FM
Dependability is reliable and can be trusted to fulfill obligations and meet expectations consistently.	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Ownership shows responsibility and commitment towards the role and tasks he/she is involved in projects.	3.83	FM	3.76	FM	3.80	FM
Reliability delivers quality work and performs predictably and consistently.	4.00	FM	3.77	FM	3.89	FM
Duty manifests a sense of accountability towards fulfilling their responsibilities and obligations, especially in a professional or organizational context.	3.83	FM	3.78	FM	3.81	FM
General Assessment	3.87	FM	3.77	FM	3.82	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Responsibility was Fully Manifested (3.82) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head delivers quality work and performs predictably and consistently” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.89**. On the other hand, the indicators “the school head is reliable and can be trusted to fulfill obligations and meet expectations consistently” and “the school head shows responsibility and commitment towards the role and tasks he/she is involved in projects” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.80**.

School heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit a strong manifestation of leadership quality in the realm of responsibility. Their constant delivery of high-quality work, sense of accountability, and dedication to their responsibilities show that they are aware of both their personal and organizational responsibilities. However, there can be room for enhancement in terms of continually being able to be counted on and trusted to uphold commitments and meet expectations. This implies that while the school heads in the division demonstrate commendable responsibility and leadership qualities, there is room for growth in terms of strengthening trust and reliability in delivering results consistently. They may increase trust among their coworkers, employees, and stakeholders by regularly surpassing expectations. This trust will not only enhance their effectiveness as leaders but also foster a culture of liability and dependability within the school community. Moreover, by actively working towards fulfilling obligations and meeting expectations, they can create a culture of excellence and reliability and set a

positive example for others.

Breevaart and Zacher (2019) found that trust in the leader was a positive predictor of perceived leader effectiveness. The study's findings highlighted the importance of trust as a foundation for effective leadership. Leaders were seen as being more effective in their roles when their subordinates trusted them. This might have a significant impact on several organizational outcomes, including employee dedication, involvement, and performance in general.

Table 1.17

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Security

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Confidence exudes confidence in his/her abilities despite uncertainties. .	3.83	FM	3.77	FM	3.80	FM
Trust can place confidence on others based on credibility, reliability, and competence.	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Safety shows the feeling of being protected from harm or danger and creates an environment to support everyone in the community.	3.83	FM	3.78	FM	3.81	FM
Protection makes himself/herself safe and provides supports and assistance to others in times of need.	3.67	FM	3.79	FM	3.73	FM
Stability shows an image of security, steadiness, and reliability, and he/she maintains consistency and continuity over time.	3.83	FM	3.80	FM	3.82	FM
General Assessment	3.83	FM	3.78	FM	3.81	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Security was Fully Manifested (3.81) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head can place confidence in others based on credibility, reliability, and competence” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.88**. On the other hand, “the school head makes himself/herself safe and provides support and assistance to others in times of need” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.73**.

School heads in the public elementary schools in cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit a strong manifestation of security. They can place confidence in others based on credibility, reliability, and competence. However, there could be room for enhancement in terms of making himself/herself safe and providing support and assistance to others in times of need. This indicates that, despite the school leaders' outstanding leadership skills in security-related matters there is room for ensuring their safety while offering support and assistance to others is fundamental to effective leadership. It encompasses values such as responsibility, empathy, resilience, and collaboration, all of which contribute to a

healthy and thriving school environment.

According to Aydođdu (2023), the school head is primarily responsible for the safety of the students. School heads who were aware of this responsibility took measures by evaluating the occupational health and safety, the physical, psychological, and social security of the student both within the scope of the legislation and the risks specific to the institution. When taking these measures, it considered the available opportunities, economic opportunities, and personnel situations school administrators and teachers needed to demonstrate.

Table 1.18

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Self-Discipline

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X [—]	VI	X [—]	VI	X [—]	VI
Self-control has regulated emotions, thoughts, and behaviors, and he/she can resist impulses and distractions. .	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Self-regulation capable of managing his/her own learning and performance, including setting goals, monitoring progress, and adjusting strategies as needed.	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Perseverance maintains focus and motivation toward achieving the goal despite setbacks and challenges.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
Willpower provides self-regulation to overcome derailment in achieving difficult objectives.	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Self-improvement advocates life-long learning to improve knowledge, skills, and abilities. .	4.00	FM	3.77	FM	3.89	FM
General Assessment	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Self-Discipline was Fully Manifested (3.90) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicators “The school head delivers quality work and performs predictably and consistently” and “The school head maintains focus and motivation toward achieving the goal despite setbacks and challenges” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head advocates life-long learning to improve knowledge, skills, and abilities” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.89**.

It indicates that the school heads in public elementary schools in cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate strong self-discipline as a crucial leadership quality. They

maintain focus and motivation toward achieving the goal despite setbacks and challenges. However, there is room for improvement in advocating life-long learning to improve knowledge, skills, and abilities.

It implies that promoting lifelong learning in leadership is fundamental to developing flexible, creative, and successful leaders who can encourage, inspire, and propel the success of their organizations in a world that is constantly changing.

According to Morin (2023), having a growth mindset is the cornerstone of lifelong learning. People were inherently interested and resilient because they believed that skills and knowledge could be developed with commitment and hard work. An unquenchable curiosity for learning and discovery was fostered by this way of thinking. A school head who was dedicated to lifelong learning and actively sought out new experiences, information, and abilities had an impact that goes well beyond their professional growth. It had a positive impact on all members of the school community, including staff, students, instructors, and stakeholders, by fostering an environment that values learning, innovation, and excellence.

Table 1.19

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Servanthood

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X [̄]	VI	X [̄]	VI	X [̄]	VI
Modesty recognizes others' accomplishments and individual contributions in achieving a common goal. .	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Altruism selflessly cares for others and provide priority over the needs of others before his/her own.	4.00	FM	3.76	FM	3.88	FM
Selflessness provides actions that are not self-serving but for the needs of others.	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM
Generosity generously provides resources for others without expecting anything in return.	4.00	FM	3.80	FM	3.90	FM
Empathy shows understanding of feeling of others and responds with compassion as a support. .	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
General Assessment	4.00	FM	3.79	FM	3.90	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Servanthood was Fully Manifested (3.90) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head shows an understanding of the feelings of others and responds with

compassion as a support” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head selflessly cares for others and provides priority over the needs of others before his/her own” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.88**.

Public elementary school heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate strong leadership qualities rooted in servanthood. They show understanding of the feelings of others and respond with compassion as a support. While they exhibit commendable servanthood-related leadership qualities, there is room for growth in consistently placing the needs of others above their own. They selflessly care for others and provide priority over the needs of others before his/her own.

Cavazotte et al. (2021) found that the ethical standards and altruism of real leaders had a unique impact on frontline workers' psychological capital and civic engagement. Although selflessness directly affected employees' civic engagement, morality had an impact on psychological capital. Furthermore, the association between genuine leader qualities and frontline workers' participation in and adherence to safety procedures was mediated by psychological capital and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Reliability and the needs of others came before self-interest or advantage for effective leaders.

Table 1.20

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Teachability

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X [̄]	VI	X [̄]	VI	X [̄]	VI
Openness openly accepts fresh ideas, perspectives, and experiences as feedback.	4.00	FM	3.82	FM	3.91	FM
Willingness to Learn acquires knowledge enthusiastically and is eager about acquiring new knowledge, skills, and experiences and is committed to continuous learning.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
Humility recognizes self-limitations and mistakes and is receptive to feedback and constructive criticism.	4.00	FM	3.85	FM	3.93	FM
Curiosity desires in exploring and discovering new knowledge, ideas, and experiences.	4.00	FM	3.82	FM	3.91	FM
Coachability is receptive guidance from others and is willing to learn and improve.	4.00	FM	3.83	FM	3.92	FM
General Assessment	4.00	FM	3.83	FM	3.92	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Teachability was **Fully Manifested (3.92)** as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicator “The school head recognizes self-limitations and mistakes and is receptive to feedback and constructive criticism” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.93**. On the other hand, the indicators “The school head openly accepts fresh ideas, perspectives, and experiences as feedback”, “The school head acquires knowledge enthusiastically and is eager about acquiring new knowledge, skills, and experiences and is committed to continuous learning” and “The school head desires in exploring and discovering new knowledge, ideas, and experiences” received the lowest composite mean score of responses with **3.91**.

Public elementary school heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate a strong manifestation of now-normal leadership qualities in the realm of teachability. They recognize self-limitations and mistakes and are receptive to feedback and constructive criticism. However, there is room for enhancement in terms of being more receptive to fresh viewpoints and experiences as well as criticism and feedback. Acquiring knowledge enthusiastically and is eager to acquire new knowledge, skills, and experiences and is committed to continuous learning and desires to explore and discover new knowledge, ideas, and experiences.

This suggests that while the school heads have remarkable leadership traits associated with teachability, there is space for improvement in terms of increasing their openness to different viewpoints and experiences. By actively seeking out fresh viewpoints and ideas, they may deepen their understanding and encourage creativity within the school community.

Gerolamo et al. (2020) highlighted the importance of open leadership, which is defined by effective communication and the capacity to provide and accept feedback, in the era Leaders were expected to demonstrate an openness to embracing new ideas, diverse viewpoints, and new concepts. They also need to be receptive to advice and helpful criticism.

Table 1.21

Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads as assessed by Teachers and School Heads in terms of Vision

Indicators The school head ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X	VI	X	VI	X	VI
Foresight has an ability to anticipate future trends, events, and opportunities to plan and prepare accordingly. .	3.67	FM	3.82	FM	3.75	FM
Strategic Thinking provides, develops, and implements effective plans and strategies creatively.	3.67	FM	3.79	FM	3.73	FM
Innovation provides value and solves problems by generating and implementing new ideas, products, or processes.	3.67	FM	3.77	FM	3.72	FM
Future Orientation can anticipate and plan for future events and circumstances.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM

Goal setting shows understanding of SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) goals.	4.00	FM	3.81	FM	3.91	FM
General Assessment	3.80	FM	3.80	FM	3.80	FM

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Fully Manifested (FM) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Manifested (M) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Partially Manifested (PM) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Not Manifested (NM)

Servanthood was Fully Manifested (3.80) as to the level of manifestation of the 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads as assessed by teachers and themselves. All indicators were verbally interpreted as **Fully Manifested**. The indicators “The school head can anticipate and plan for future events and circumstances” and “The school head shows an understanding of SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) goals” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.91**. On the other hand, the indicator “The school head provides value and solves problems by generating and implementing new ideas, products, or processes” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.72**.

Public elementary school heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate strong leadership qualities in the realm of vision. Their ability to anticipate and plan for future events and circumstances and they show an understanding of SMART (specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound) goals. While they exhibit commendable vision-related leadership qualities, there is room for growth in providing value and solving problems by generating and implementing new ideas, products, or processes. By keeping up with current updates and practices, they can modify their vision to better serve the evolving requirements of their community and students. By actively seeking out fresh concepts and promoting a mindset of continuous improvement, school administrators may strengthen their demonstration of vision-connected leadership abilities and guarantee that their instructional initiatives continue to have an impact.

Kantabutra (2020) A key goal should be to bring together strong management and visionary leadership into a unified system that allows both to work together effectively for the success of the organization.

However, an article entitled “The Leadership of Innovation” (2023) highlighted that a clear vision and purpose from effective leaders inspired teams to pursue excellence. Furthermore, those who welcome innovation served as the catalysts that upended the status quo and led their organizations into new and exciting areas.

Table 2

Test of Significant Difference between the Assessment of the School Heads and Teachers on the Level of Manifestation of 21st-Century Leadership Qualities of School Heads

Variables	t test	P value	Remarks	Decision
Character	3.99	.230	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Charisma	4.944	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Commitment	.651	.516	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Communication	.327	.744	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Competence	4.428	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Courage	.677	.500	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Discern	.657	.512	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Focus	.720	.472	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Generosity	3.722	.002	Significant	Reject Ho
Initiative	.423	.673	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Listening	7.320	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Passion	2.357	.047	Significant	Reject Ho
Problem Solving	.913	.363	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Relationships	7.272	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Responsibility	.573	.567	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Security	.320	.749	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Self -Discipline	6.852	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Servanthood	6.662	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Teachability	5.927	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Vision	.009	.992	Not Significant	Accept Ho

There was no significant difference between the assessment of school heads and teachers on the level of manifestation of 21st-century leadership skills of school heads on the character, commitment, communication, courage, discernment, focus, initiative, problem-solving, responsibility, security, and vision. The probability values were **.230, .516, .744, .500, .512, .472, .673, .363, 567, .749, and .992**, respectively, which were all greater than the level of significance at .05, thus accepting the null hypothesis.

This means that the School Heads and Teachers among Public Elementary Schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City have the same perception regarding the Manifestation Level of Leadership Qualities in terms of Character, Commitment, Communication, Courage, Discernment, Focus, Initiative, Problem, Solving, Responsibility, Security, And Vision.

On the other hand, there was a significant difference between the assessment of school heads and teachers on the level of manifestation of 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads on the charisma, competence, generosity, listening, passion, attitude, relationships, discipline, servanthood, and teachability. The probability values were **.000, .000, .002, .000, .047, .018, .000, .000, .000**, and **.000** respectively, which were all less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

This suggests that in the currently prevalent leadership framework, school heads and teachers have different perspectives or interpretations on Charisma, Competence, Generosity, Listening, Passion, Attitude, Relationships, Discipline, Servanthood, and Teachability. These findings show that school heads and teachers generally agree on how to perceive leadership traits, but they also point to the need for more research and comprehension of various perspectives on charisma, competence, generosity, listening, passion, attitude, relationships, discipline, servanthood, and teachability. Addressing these differences in insight can contribute to a more cohesive and integrated approach to leadership development and implementation in Cluster 7 Calamba City.

According to Grieser (2024) stated that leading with passion is one thing; motivating others to feel the same way is quite another. By demonstrating sincere enthusiasm and communicating the organization's mission and how it made a difference, leaders motivated their team members to be passionate.

Moreover, according to Vannier (2023), leaders could contribute to a better, cooperative workplace in addition to improving team performance by integrating generosity into their leadership style. As they proceeded, they had to keep in mind the positive effects of giving and tried to be leaders who inspire, empower, and lead.

Additionally, Žvinklys (2024) stated that establishing a clear direction and a feeling of purpose could enhance team performance. By fostering an atmosphere of open communication and trust, it could increase team engagement. By encouraging personal development and appreciation, it could improve the work experience for employees.

Table 3.1

Level of Competency of Public Elementary Teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Knowing and Understanding What to Teach

Indicators The teacher ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
1. has thorough comprehension of the subject matter.	4.00	VG	3.85	VG	3.93	VG
2. creates curriculum aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives.	3.83	VG	3.79	VG	3.81	VG
3. requires the understanding of the competency standards aligned with the curriculum objectives and learning outcomes.	3.83	VG	3.89	VG	3.86	VG
4. demonstrates expertise about various instructional strategies and methods that best convey specific concepts.	3.83	VG	3.78	VG	3.81	VG
5. designs skillfully assessments that accurately measure student understanding.	3.83	VG	3.83	VG	3.83	VG
General Assessment	3.87	VG	3.83	VG	3.85	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Poor (P)

Knowing and Understanding What to Teach was Very Good (3.85) as to the level of competency of public elementary teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers. All the indicators were verbally interpreted as **Very Good**. The indicator “The teacher has a thorough comprehension of the subject matter and creates curriculum-aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.93**. On the other hand, the indicators “The teacher creates curriculum-aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives requires the understanding of the competency standards aligned with the curriculum objectives and learning outcomes” and “The teacher

demonstrates expertise about various instructional strategies and methods that best convey specific concepts.” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.81**.

It highlights the strong level of teachers’ competency in terms of Knowing and understanding what to teach within the public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City. The teacher has a thorough comprehension of the subject matter and creates curriculum-aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives. However, there is room for improvement in terms of further enhancing curriculum-aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives requires the understanding of the competency standards aligned with the curriculum objectives and learning outcomes. The teacher demonstrates expertise in various instructional strategies and methods that best convey specific concepts.

According to Gupta (2023), teachers are essential to the curriculum development process because they have been contributing their knowledge, skills, and understanding of their students to the process. They offered invaluable assistance in determining learning objectives, choosing relevant materials, and creating effective teaching methods for their pupils.

Moreover, as stated by Persaud (2023), students can draw meaningful connections between what they have learned in the classroom and real-world scenarios when teachers employ instructional strategies. Students could showcase their expertise and make independent course corrections, when necessary, through these opportunities. The use of instructional strategies by teachers also helped them monitor and evaluate student performance more effectively by providing them with a variety of assessment options.

Table 3.2

Level of Competency of Public Elementary Teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Helping Students Learn

Indicators The teacher ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
1. uses teaching techniques and instructional strategies to fulfill the needs of learners.	3.83	VG	3.87	VG	3.85	VG
2. adapts instruction to meet the needs of each student.	3.83	VG	3.89	VG	3.86	VG
3. improves their teaching methods and delivers feedback on time.	3.83	VG	3.83	VG	3.83	VG
4. has clear routines, structured spaces, and accessible resources that are imperative for fostering an effective learning environment, that optimally supports student learning.	4.00	VG	3.83	VG	3.92	VG
5. supports ways to improve areas of opportunity for pupils.	4.00	VG	3.88	VG	3.94	VG
General Assessment	3.90	VG	3.86	VG	3.88	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Poor (P)

Helping Students to Learn was **Very Good (3.88)** as to the level of competency of public elementary teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers. All the indicators were verbally interpreted as **Very Good**. The indicator “The teacher supports ways to improve areas of opportunity for pupils” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.94**. On the other hand, the indicator “the school head improves their teaching methods and delivers feedback on time” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.83**.

It suggests that the public elementary schools in Cluster 7, Calamba City demonstrate a strong level of teachers’ competency in terms of Helping students to learn. The teacher supports ways to improve areas of opportunity for pupils. They allow students to enhance their skills and knowledge by giving different activities that showcase their abilities. However, there is room for further enhancement on the teachers improving their teaching methods and delivering feedback by embracing these strategies and committing to continuous improvement, teachers can enhance their teaching methods and feedback delivery, ultimately creating more effective and impactful learning experiences for their students.

As SEAMEO INNOTECH (2020) teachers promoted academic excellence by encouraging engaged and knowledgeable learners in their classrooms. This goal could be achieved by truly getting to know one’s students, understanding the best teaching and learning strategies for them, and providing meaningful feedback about how they were learning and what areas needed improvement. Educators need to keep this objective in mind when planning their lessons and creating assessments or activities; not just teaching for the sake of teaching, but rather personalizing instruction based on individual student needs.

Table 3.3

Level of Competency of Public Elementary Teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Engaging the Community

Indicators The teacher ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI	\bar{X}	VI
1. develops rapport with parents and the community through involvement to school and community.	4.00	VG	3.87	VG	3.94	VG
2. initiates activities align with the barangay development plan focused on safe and supportive learning environment.	3.67	VG	3.74	VG	3.71	VG
3. interacts with the larger community to advance education and form partnerships with nearby companies and organizations.	3.50	VG	3.74	VG	3.62	VG
4. informs parents and guardians of their child's development and includes them in the learning process on a proactive basis.	4.00	VG	3.87	VG	3.94	VG

5. participates in community activities and events such as outreach program, Gender, and Development, Clean and Green Drive and others.

	3.83	VG	3.79	VG	3.81	VG
General Assessment	3.80	VG	3.80	VG	3.80	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Poor (P)

Engaging the Community was Very Good (3.80) as to the level of competency of public elementary teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers. All the indicators were verbally interpreted as **Very Good**. The indicators “The teacher develops a rapport with parents and the community through involvement to school and community” and “The teacher informs parents and guardians of their child’s development and includes them in the learning process on a proactive basis” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.94**. On the other hand, the indicator “The teacher interacts with the larger community to advance education and form partnerships with nearby companies and organizations.” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.62**.

Public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate a high level of teachers’ competency in terms of Engaging the community. The teacher develops a rapport with parents and the community through involvement in school and community. The teacher informs parents and guardians of their child’s development and includes them in the learning process on a proactive basis. However, there is still potential for improvement in teachers interacting with the larger community to advance education and form partnerships with nearby companies and organizations. By leveraging the resources, expertise, and support of external partners, teachers can create more engaging, relevant, and impactful learning experiences for their students.

According to NCLSSE (2024), as teachers interact with their students, they play a very important role in establishing a safe, supportive learning environment. Positive teacher-student relationships could have long-lasting effects on the social, emotional, and academic development of youth. Teachers could improve the school’s environment by building relationships with students and staff throughout the school which could lead to the prevention of physical violence, bullying, and emotional abuse in their classrooms.

Table 3.4

Level of Competency of Public Elementary Teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Becoming a Better Teacher Every Day

Indicators The teacher ...	Heads		Teachers		Composite	
	X̄	VI	X̄	VI	X̄	VI
1. continuously seeks opportunities for professional growth.	3.83	VG	3.84	VG	3.84	VG
2. finds areas for improvement and make the necessary adjustments by engaging in self-reflection and self-assessment.	4.00	VG	3.85	VG	3.93	VG

3. demonstrates flexibility and receptiveness to new ideas because the educational landscape is ever-changing.	4.00	VG	3.83	VG	3.92	VG
4. Shows positivism in receiving feedback from peers, mentors, and students.	4.00	VG	3.87	VG	3.94	VG
5. seeks out mentorship and advice from seasoned teachers. With peers, exchange tactics and experiences to improve teaching abilities.	4.00	VG	3.87	VG	3.94	VG
General Assessment	3.97	VG	3.85	VG	3.91	VG

Legend: 3.25 - 4.00 Strongly Agree – Very Good (VG) 2.50 - 3.24 Agree – Good (G) 1.75 - 2.49 Disagree – Fair (F) 1.00 - 1.74 Strongly Disagree- Poor (P)

Becoming a Better Teacher Every Day was **Very Good (3.91)** as to the level of competency of public elementary teachers in Cluster 7, Calamba City as assessed by school heads and teachers. All the indicators were verbally interpreted as **Very Good**. The indicators “The teacher shows positivism in receiving feedback from peers, mentors, and students” and “the teacher seeks out mentorship and advice from seasoned teachers. With peers, exchange tactics and experiences to improve teaching abilities” yielded the highest composite mean score of **3.94**. On the other hand, “the teacher continuously seeks opportunities for professional growth” received the lowest composite mean score of **3.84**.

Public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate a high level of teacher competency in terms of becoming a better teacher every day. The teacher shows positivism in receiving feedback from peers, mentors, and students. The teacher seeks out mentorship and advice from seasoned teachers. With peers, exchange tactics and experiences to improve teaching abilities. However, there is still potential for improvement for teachers in seeking opportunities for professional growth. By investing in their professional development, teachers ultimately contribute to the success and well-being of their students and the overall improvement of the education system.

Consequently, the study of Owusu (2022) concluded that teacher quality and other aspects of professional development improved teacher knowledge, which in turn improved student academic achievement. In response to the deficiencies in their professional competencies, the study suggested, among other things, that educators be encouraged to participate in a variety of professional development activities.

Table 4

Test of Significant Difference between the Assessment of the School Head and Teachers on the Level of Teachers’ Competency

Variables	t-test	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Knowing and Understanding What to Teach	.306	.760	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Helping Students Learn	.367	.714	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Engaging the Community	.010	.991	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Becoming a better teacher every day	2.835	.016	Significant	Reject Ho

There was no significant difference between the assessment of school heads and teachers on the level of teachers' competency in Knowing and Understanding What to Teach, Helping Students to Learn, and Engaging the Community. The probability values were **.760**, **.714**, and **.991**, respectively, which were all greater than the level of significance at .05, thus accepting the null hypothesis.

On the other hand, there was a significant difference between the assessment of school heads and teachers on the level of manifestation of 21st-century leadership skills of school heads on Becoming a Better Teacher Every Day. The probability value was **.016** which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus rejecting the null hypothesis.

This indicates that the school heads and teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City had the same assessment about the level of teachers' competency in Knowing and Understanding What to Teach and Helping students learn and engage in the community. This also suggests that school heads and teachers may have different perspectives about becoming a better teacher every day. This shows that they point to the need for more research and comprehension of various perspectives on becoming a better teacher every day. Addressing this insight can contribute to a more comprehensive and unified strategy for the development and application of the teachers' competency in Cluster 7 Calamba City.

According to UNESCO (2022), to guarantee high-quality education, educators needed to be proficient in both the "pedagogical content knowledge"—a body of information made up of concepts, theories, facts, and vocabulary—and the "content knowledge"—a body of knowledge they impart which has a pronouncedly favorable impact on student performance especially that it was interconnected with the development of 21st-century skills.

Moreover, the results of Afzal's (2020) study showed that the understanding that community service in schools not only earned additional credit for students but also improved them as citizens was the foundation for the knowledge of the need to promote it. This implied that helping students to learn and engage in the ability to boost strong familial links to their localities. Furthermore, it encouraged pupils to obtain a diverse range of academic and intellectual skills to enable them to understand and deal with the difficulties they dealt with daily.

According to Dicu (2022), self-reflection is an effective technique that may be learned and applied regularly. Critical thinking can lead to self-improvement through it. It will begin taking notes on what worked and what didn't, identify your preconceptions, and generally engage in a deeper level of introspection. Applying self-awareness and consciousness to your work will also help you reflect more thoroughly on the welfare of your students and their openness to the curriculum.

Table 5.1

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Qualities of School Head and Public Elementary Teachers' Competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Knowing and Understanding What to Teach

Variables	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Character	.554**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Charisma	.492**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Commitment	.506**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Communication	.538**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Competence	.586**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Courage	.465**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Discern	.506**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Focus	.477**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Generosity	.504**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Initiative	.520**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Listening	.571**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Passion	.504**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Attitude	.490**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Problem Solving	.504**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Relationships	.490**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Responsibility	.562**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Security	.563**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Self-Discipline	.540**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Servanthood	.542**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Teachability	.540**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Vision	.508**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

There was a significant relationship between Knowing and Understanding what to teach and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City. The probability values were all **0.000** which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The r value lies between **0.41** to **0.75**, then it was said to have a moderately small to high positive correlation.

It indicates that there is a direct relationship between the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of the school head and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Knowing and Understanding What to Teach. This also indicates that the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of the School Head, the greater the public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Knowing and Understanding What to Teach.

According to Culdaz (2023), the standard of educational leadership had a significant impact on how pupils learn, and education was a foundation of society. The ability to impact and change learning environments was possessed by educational leaders like principals and school administrators. This research endeavored to investigate how educational leadership might enhance the quality of the learning process. It explored the different facets of successful educational leadership, such as organizational management, educational leadership, and fostering a supportive school environment.

This study looked at the best practices and research in educational leadership to clarify how effective leadership could improve learning outcomes by fostering student involvement and well-being, improving teaching and learning, and so forth.

Table 5.2

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Qualities of School Head and Public Elementary Teachers' Competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Helping Students Learn

Variables	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Character	.441**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Charisma	.433**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Commitment	.411**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Communication	.523**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Competence	.452**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Courage	.372**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Discern	.394**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Focus	.398**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Generosity	.497**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Initiative	.439**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Listening	.493**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Passion	.425**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Positive Attitude	.417**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Problem Solving	.388**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Relationships	.377**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Responsibility	.407**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Security	.463**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Self-Discipline	.512**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Servanthood	.389**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Teachability	.450**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Vision	.381**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

There was a significant relationship between Helping Students Learn and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City. The probability values were all **0.000** which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The r values lie between **0.41** to **0.75**, then it was said to be a moderately small to a high positive correlation.

It indicates that there is an extensive relationship between the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of School Heads and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Helping Students Learn. This also indicates that the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of the School Head, the greater the public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Helping Students to Learn.

As stated by Lyssiotis (2021), positive school climates could be established and sustained by school leaders. Student empowerment was recognized to boost school

pride, instructors' work, and student learning immediately in an environment of respect, trust, and collaboration. Effective leadership created an environment that fostered student engagement, motivation, and academic success, ultimately preparing students for future success in school and beyond.

Table 5.3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Qualities of School Head and Public Elementary Teachers' Competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Engaging the Community

Variables	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Character	.472**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Charisma	.458**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Commitment	.380**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Communication	.490**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Competence	.515**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Courage	.384**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Discern	.471**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Focus	.449**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Generosity	.441**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Initiative	.410**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Listening	.441**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Passion	.448**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Attitude	.443**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Problem Solving	.509**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Relationships	.473**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Responsibility	.500**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Security	.492**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Self-Discipline	.460**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Servanthood	.494**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Teachability	.476**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Vision	.453**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

There was a significant relationship between Engaging the Community and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City. The probability values were all **0.000** which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The r values lie between **0.41** to **0.75**, then it was said to be a moderately small to high positive correlation.

It indicates that there is a linear association between the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of School Heads and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Engaging the Community. This also indicates that the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of the School Head, the greater the public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba city in terms of Engaging the community.

Dare (2022) revealed that when leaders develop the community's life by function

and purpose, in addition to understanding it, the community would live up to its potential. Making a positive difference in the lives of others was the highest purpose. An effective community leader would facilitate connections and ideas exchanges among members of the community so that individuals could benefit from one another's experiences. They would assist individuals in cultivating a strong sense of social duty and community. Leaders inspire others to support one another. They inspired and motivated others, set a clear vision, empowered community members, and guided them toward common goals, fostering a sense of ownership and commitment.

Table 5.4

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Qualities of School Head and Public Elementary Teachers' Competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Becoming a Better Teacher Every Day

Variables	r value	p value	Remarks	Decision
Character	.465**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Charisma	.390**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Commitment	.346**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Communication	.434**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Competence	.465**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Courage	.379**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Discern	.392**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Focus	.412**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Generosity	.475**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Initiative	.389**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Listening	.458**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Passion	.389**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Positive-Attitude	.433**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Problem Solving	.394**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Relationships	.407**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Responsibility	.422**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Security	.462**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Self-Discipline	.455**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Servanthood	.468**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Teachability	.437**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
Vision	.401**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

There was a significant relationship between Becoming a Better Teacher Every day and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City. The probability values were all **0.000** which was less than the level of significance at .05, thus the null hypothesis was rejected. The r values lie between **0.41** to **0.75**, then it was said to be a moderately small to high positive correlation.

It indicates that there is a direct association between the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of School Heads and public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Becoming a Better Teacher Every Day. This also indicates that the higher the level of manifestation of the 21st-century qualities of the School Head, the better the public elementary teachers' competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City in terms of Becoming a Better Teacher Every day.

As cited by Singh (2024), teacher education and educational leadership entail the direction and assistance given by leaders in educational establishments to support instructors' professional development. Education leaders have overseen encouraging teacher collaboration, established a favorable learning environment, and creating an environment that values innovation and progress. They were essential to forming the objectives and vision of the institution, as well as in offering teachers direction and advice for their professional growth. Improving student outcomes, increasing teacher effectiveness, and fostering a favorable school climate.

Table 5.5

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Manifestation of the 21st-Century Qualities of School Head and Public Elementary Teachers' Competency in Cluster 7 of Calamba City

Independent Variables	Independent Variables	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Manifestation of the 21st century qualities	Teachers' competency	.521**	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

This implies that the higher the 21st-century leadership qualities, the higher the teachers' competency. Recognizing the significant relationship between 21st-century leadership qualities and teachers' competency highlights the importance of developing and nurturing effective leadership skills among school heads and teachers. This can involve providing professional maturity opportunities, mentoring programs, and resources to enhance leadership capabilities. These findings also emphasize the importance for educational institutions to provide leadership development activities top priority and aid school leaders in their endeavors to enhance teacher competence. The competence of teachers is essential for fostering student achievement, creating a supportive learning environment, and promoting a culture of lifelong learning within schools. By prioritizing competence, teachers can positively impact the lives of their students and contribute to the overall success of the education system. Overall, the results suggest that 21st-century leadership qualities are essential for improving teachers' competency, and investing in leadership development can contribute to the overall improvement of public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City.

Ozgenel (2020) asserted that teacher performance and the effective leadership qualities of school heads had a moderately favorable association, and the effective leadership qualities of school heads strongly predicted teacher performance.

Additionally, according to Sarwar et al. (2022), the findings revealed that the leadership style of the head of the school improved the performance of the teachers. A robust and statistically significant correlation was found between the leadership style of college principals and the performance of their teachers.

Table 6

The Proposed Program

“I-LEAD- Embracing the 21st Century Leadership Qualities”

KEY RESULT AREA	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	TIME FRAME	PERSONS INVOLVED	SOURCE OF FUND	SUCCESS INDICATORS
Intensifying connections and communications through	<p>The program aims for the school heads to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Foster leaders to have a strong feeling of loyalty, dedication, and commitment to the school community. ● Promote outstanding communication to build teamwork, understanding, and common objectives. 	<p>Activities that promote involvement and creating ties within school community including team-building exercises, collaborative projects, and communication training.</p>	<p>July 2024- August 2024</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical Experts ● School Heads ● Faculty ● HR 	<p>School Funds</p>	<p>80% of the attendees were fostered with a sense of loyalty, dedication, and commitment to the school community.</p> <p>80% of the attendees were possessed outstanding communication to improve teamwork, understanding and common objectives.</p>
Lead Actions and Task-focused	<p>The program aims for the school heads to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Encourage leaders to initiate and anticipate possible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Scenario and Strategic workshop to initiate a possible problem and take the necessary actions and capacity of 	<p>August 2024 September 2024</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical Experts ● School Heads ● Faculty 	<p>School Funds</p>	

	<p>problems and take the necessary actions to prevent or exploit them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Strengthen leaders' capacity to effectively plan, organize, and utilize resources to achieve objectives. 	<p>leaders to effectively plan, organize, and utilize resources to achieve goals.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● HR 		<p>80% of the attendees were encouraged to initiate and anticipate possible problems and take the necessary actions to prevent or exploit them.</p> <p>80% of the attendees were strengthened capacity to effectively plan, organize, and utilize resources to achieve objectives.</p>
Encourage Risk-taking and Security	<p>The program aims for the school heads to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Motivate leaders to identify and accept the right risks in the pursuit of goals and achievement. ● Promote a sense of safety, stability, dependability, and continuous to be reliable and consistency across time. 	<p>Risk assessment and management workshops to help leaders develop an effective plan for taking measured risks.</p>	<p>September 2024-October 2024</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical Experts ● School Heads ● Faculty ● HR 	<p>School Funds</p>	<p>80% of the attendees were motivated to identify and accept the right risks in the pursuit of goals and achievement.</p> <p>80% of the attendees were displayed a sense of safety, stability, dependability, and continuity to be reliable and consistent across time.</p>
Analytical Thinking and Responsibility toward the	<p>The program aims for the school heads to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Encourage leaders to provide evaluation and analysis of information 	<p>Interactive sessions and exercises to stimulate analytical thinking and commitment towards the role and tasks, he/she is involved in projects.</p>	<p>October 2024-November 2024</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical Experts ● School Heads ● Faculty ● HR 	<p>School Funds</p>	<p>80% of the attendees were conducted an objective and logical evaluation and analysis of the information.</p>

		objectively and logically.					
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrate responsibility and commitment towards the role and tasks he/she is involved in in projects. 					80% of the attendees were showed responsibility and commitment towards the role and tasks he/she is involved in in projects.
Desire on Comprehensive curriculum	The program aims for the school heads to:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Craft curriculum aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives. 	Employ Brainstorming Sessions in crafting the curriculum-aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives	October 2024- November 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical Experts • School Heads • Faculty • HR 	School Funds	80% of the attendees were crafted curriculum aligned materials to meet the needs of students and learning objectives.

Based on the comprehensive examination of leadership qualities and indicators with the lowest means, a leadership mentoring program is now being proposed. The program, titled "I-LEAD: captures the fundamental principles of this endeavor, concentrating on the need to equip leaders to conquer challenges and truly flourish in their particular roles. I-LEAD was an acronym and below is the title's breakdown and relevance to the program in more detail:

I – Intensifying Connections: This letter represents the devotion to building a feeling of commitment, enthusiasm, and camaraderie throughout the school community. Establishing and maintaining connections with all stakeholders is crucial for leaders, necessitating clear and efficient communication.

L – Lead Actions: The inclusion of this letter demonstrated the program's establishment of an innovative and proactive leader. It helped them to initiate and anticipate possible problems and take necessary action to the problem.

E -Encourage Risk-Taking: This letter emphasized that the program recognized the critical role that measured risk-taking played in achieving goals and achievement. Considering uncertainty, the importance of adaptability, sensitivity, and the ability to form reliable conclusions was emphasized.

A – Analytical Thinking: The presence of this letter highlighted the program fostered innovation, promoted collaboration, built resilience, and drove personal and professional growth. By cultivating strong problem-solving skills, individuals can navigate challenges, seize opportunities, and achieve their full potential in all aspects of life.

D – Desire for comprehensive curriculum: This letter emphasized that the program recognized the crucial designing of the curriculum. It has promoted the development of a specific skill set, provides tailored learning paths, stresses real-world application, encourages ongoing growth, supports organizational objectives, and helps create a pipeline of future leaders.

The title of the program "I-LEAD Embracing 21st Century Leadership Qualities " captured all the main ideas and indicators previously discussed, all the while conveying a feeling of improvement, growth, and outstanding leadership in the given environment. It communicated the program's goal.

Conclusions

The previously mentioned findings have led to the following conclusions:

1. That the public elementary school heads in Cluster 7 Calamba City exhibit strong displays of 21st-century leadership qualities across various areas.

2. That that the School Heads and Teachers in Public Elementary Schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City have the same perception regarding the Manifestation Level of 21st-century Leadership Qualities in terms of character, commitment, communication, courage, discernment, focus, initiative, problem-solving, responsibility, and vision. However, they have different perceptions in terms of charisma, competence, generosity, listening, passion-attitude, relationships, discipline, servanthood, and teachability.

3. That the public elementary teachers in Cluster 7 Calamba City demonstrate high capability in various abilities.

4. That the school heads and teachers in public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City have the same perception regarding the teachers' competency level in terms of Knowing and Understanding What to Teach, Helping Students Learn, and Engaging the Community. However, they have different perceptions in terms of knowing and understanding what to teach.

5. That the 21st-century leadership qualities have a significant high direct association, connection, or link with teachers' competency in public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City. The higher the level of manifestation of 21st-century leadership qualities of school heads, the higher the teachers' competence.

6. That a leadership mentoring program called "I-LEAD: Embracing the 21st Century Leadership Quality" needs to be implemented to improve leadership attributes that are less manifested by the school leaders to improve teachers' competence.

Recommendations

Based on the summarized findings of the study and finalized conclusions, the following recommendations are highly encouraged:

1. To maintain and improve leadership skills in public elementary schools in Cluster 7 Calamba, the administration may offer specific training focusing on growth areas like creativity, adaptability, resilience, empathy, and time management. This fosters effective leadership, supportive environments, collaboration, and innovation. The study's findings can guide future development initiatives for ongoing improvement.

2. To enhance the leadership qualities of school heads in public elementary schools in cluster 7 Calamba City the school heads may encourage to foster continuous learning, sharing valuable things with others, building trust, creating a positive culture, resilience, compassion, and openness to feedback, The school heads can contribute to the professional growth and competency of teachers, ultimately leading to improved educational experiences and outcomes for students in Cluster 7 Calamba City.

3. To enhance the teacher's competency, in public elementary schools in cluster 7 Calamba City, the teachers may focus on instructional strategies, giving meaningful feedback to learners, community partnership, and participating in professional development.

4. To enhance the teachers' competency in public elementary schools in cluster 7 Calamba City the teacher may be encouraged to foster a level of self-awareness and consciousness about practice. Teachers can enhance their professional practice, promote student success, and contribute to a positive and supportive learning environment.

5. To enhance Public Elementary Schools in Cluster 7 Calamba City, school leaders may give themselves priority when it comes to leadership development initiatives like professional development, mentoring, and resources and cultivating effective leadership qualities that can enhance teachers' competence. These efforts drive significant improvements in teachers' competence for long-term success.

6. To assist in the achievement of the desired level of teachers' competency, both school administrators and teachers use a leadership mentoring program. This program aims to improve leadership qualities that may not be prominently displayed, thereby making a valuable contribution to teachers' competence. The leadership mentoring program called "I-LEAD: Embracing the 21st Century Leadership Qualities" may be used by Cluster 7 Calamba City.

7. For future researchers, similar studies may be conducted in private elementary schools in Calamba City to determine if comparable results can be obtained. This would allow for a comparison between the findings of the public and private sectors.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author, Estrañero, Kheycil B, declares that there are no financial, personal, or professional interests that could be perceived as influencing the research or its interpretation. No competing interests are present that would affect the objectivity, integrity, or impartiality of the study or its findings. The author confirms that all aspects of the research were conducted without any potential conflict of interest.

Acknowledgments

The researcher expresses her heartfelt gratitude to the following individuals, whose support made the completion of this study possible. In addition to a great deal of dedication and perseverance, their assistance was indispensable.

Above all, the researcher wishes to thank Almighty God for providing wisdom, health, strength, and abundant blessings throughout the completion of this thesis;

Dean Alfredo G. Perez, Jr., the Dean of the School of Graduate Studies of LCBA, for his continual encouragement, patience, and constructive suggestions throughout the research endeavor;

Dr. Ma. Lorena M. Tagala, the Research Director of LCBA, for her generosity in sharing her knowledge and her patience with all the researchers. Her genuine enthusiasm for their success is truly admirable.

Dr. Eulalia M. Javier, the researcher's adviser, and Institutional Statistician of LCBA, for her advice and academic analysis that enhanced the depth and rigor of this study. Her constant assistance, knowledge, and moral support were crucial to the study's success throughout the research process. Her steadfast commitment to excellence and encouragement of this academic growth has been immensely inspiring;

To the esteemed members of the research defense panel Dr. Melchor A. Villapando, Dean Alfredo G. Perez Jr., and Dr. Ma. Lorena M. Tagala, for their support, knowledge, and insightful feedback during our research. Their insightful comments, insightful questions, and beneficial criticisms have substantially improved and polished this work;

Laguna College of Business and Arts (LCBA), the institution, for giving the necessary resources and chances needed to carry out this research. The institution's resources and assistance were crucial to the successful completion of this thesis;

Her loving parents and siblings, for their steadfast support, understanding, sacrifices, and encouragement throughout this challenging yet rewarding journey. Their fortitude has been the researcher's greatest blessing, and she is deeply humbled by their profound love and dedication;

Her supportive friend, Laralein and colleagues, for their companionship, support, and encouragement. Reaching this milestone with them is a wonderful and delightful experience;

Her husband Jake and daughter Hailey Snow, for their unwavering patience and support during the research. Their unwavering devotion and faith in the researcher provided a steady supply of inspiration and direction;

Lastly, the researcher thanks everyone who contributed to the completion of this thesis. The author is truly appreciative and honored to have had their assistance, as their

encouragement and support have been invaluable.

REFERENCES

- Afzal, A. (2020). Impact of Community Service Learning on the Social Skills of Students. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*7(1), 55-70, 2020.DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22555/joeed.v7i1.2988>
- Alfari, T. (2024). The Crucial Role of Communication Skills in School Leadership
The Crucial Role of Communication Skills in School Leadership
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/crucial-role-communication-skills-school-leadership-aljafari-phd-4wle>
- Arrieta, G. (2020). Ready or not: the experiences of novice academic heads in school leadership. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 19(5), 78-88. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.19.5.5>
- Aydoğdu, A. (2023). School Administrators' Concerns About Student Safety at School ED629088.pdf
- Balinado, B. (2023). Leader Qualities and School Effectiveness In Public Secondary Schools In The Division Of Tanauan City In The Now Normal: Basis For Leadership Mentoring Program
- Bell, R., & Martin, J. (2019). Managerial Communication for Organizational Development https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331502420_Managerial_Communication_for_Organizational_Development
- Breevaart, K., & Zacher, H. (2019). Main and interactive effects of weekly transformational and laissez-faire leadership on followers' trust in the leader and leader effectiveness. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 92(2), 384-409. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12253>
- Brown, C., & Nwagbara, U. (2021). Leading change with the heart: exploring the relationship between emotional intelligence and transformational leadership in the era of covid-19 pandemic challenges. *Economic Insights – Trends and Challenges*, 10(73), 1-12.
- Buffone, P. (2021). Agility: an essential element of leadership for an evolving educational landscape. *FACETS*, 6, 1610-1620. <https://doi.org/10.1139/facets2021-0085>
- Cabalquinto, A. (2022). A Model of Humanistic Leadership Style in the Healthcare Industry:TheFacility<https://www.proquest.com/openview/cc765716fd5f065ca689ccf75473ab45/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Cansoy, R., & Polatcan, M. (2019). The relationship between school principals' leadership and teachers' organisational commitment: A systematic review. *Bartın University Journal of Faculty of Education*, 8(1), 1-31. 10.14686/buefad.441189
- Carr, E., Livingston, H.M., & Phillips, S. (2022). Courage: A key requirement for effective healthcare leadership. *Journal of Prosthodontic Research*, 66(4). 1-3. https://doi.org/10.2186/jpr.JPR_D_22_00209
- Castelhana, R. (2023). The Importance of Time Management in Leadership: Maximizing Your Potential for Success. The Importance of Time Management in Leadership: Maximizing Your Potential for Success <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/importance-time-management-leadership-maximizing-your-castelhana>
- Cavazotte, F., Mansur, J., & Moreno, V. (2021). Authentic leadership and sustainable operations: how leader morality and selflessness can foster frontline safety performance. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 313, 127819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127819>

- Chaudhuri, P. (2022). Instructional Strategies Used by K-12 Teachers During the COVID-19 Pandemic
<https://www.proquest.com/openview/a062f3183f2151b9a25c15eb65afae2d/1?p-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Creswell J.W., & Hirose, M. (2019). Mixed methods and survey research in family medicine and community health. *Fam Med Community Health*, 7(2). doi: 10.1136/fmch-2018-000086
- Culduz, M. (2023) The Impact of Educational Leadership in Improving the Learning Experience Promoting Crisis Management and Creative Problem-Solving Skills in Educational Leadership (pp.168-189) DOI:10.4018/978-1-6684-8332-9.ch008
- Dare, N. (2022). The Importance of Community Leadership
 The Importance of Community Leadership | by Nicky Dare | Medium
- D'Ascoli, S., & Piro, J. S. (2023). Educational servant-leaders and personal growth. *Journal of School Leadership*, 33(1), 26-49. <https://doi.org/10.1177/10526846221134001>
- Dicu, P. (2024). How To Be a Better Teacher In 2023. *How To Be a Better Teacher In 2023 – Teach Away*
- Farahnak, L. R., Ehrhart, M. G., Torres, E. M., & Aarons, G. A. (2020). The influence of transformational leadership and leader attitudes on subordinate attitudes and implementation success. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 27(1), 98-111. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1548051818824529>
- Fauth, B. (2019). The effects of teacher competence on student outcomes in elementary science education: The mediating role of teaching quality 10.1016/j.tate.2019.102882
- Fitria, H., Ahyani, N., Mahasir, M., & Hermalita, H. (2023). The Influence of Principal's Leadership and Professional Teacher's Competence on Teacher's Performance. *JMKSP*
- Gerolamo, M., Guzman, V., Kohl, H., Muschard, B., & Rozenfeld, H. (2020). Characteristics and skills of leadership in the context of industry 4.0. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 43, 543-550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2020.02.167>
- Gonzales, R. (2022). Nurse Job Satisfaction in the Midst of a Pandemic
<https://digitalrepository.unm.edu/dnp/27/>
- Grieser, R. (2024). Why Passionate Leadership Matters
www.theordinaryleader.com
- Gupta, H. (2023). An Alternative Perspective on The Teachers' Role In Curriculum Development. <https://elearningindustry.com/alternative-perspective-on-the-teachers-role-in-curriculum-development>
- Hermans, C.A.M. (2021). Discernment as predictor for transformational leadership: a study of school leaders in catholic schools in India. *Journal of Beliefs & Values*, 42(3), 393–408. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13617672.2020.1852815>
- Intoy, J. (2021). 21st Century Leadership Skills of School Heads and Personality Development of Teachers: Elements of Effective Pedagogical Skills
 DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.29050.41924
- Istiqomah, A., Suyatno S., & Maryani I. (2019). The Effect of Teacher Competencies on Student Achievement in Vocational High School 10.5296/ije.v11i4.15625
- Jakhongir, S., & Gulnora, B. (2021). The difference between educational management and educational leadership and the importance of educational responsibility. *Research Gate*, 1-22.
- Jones, D., & Davis, S. (2020). Courageous Leadership: Walking Your Talk from Wherever You Are from the Printed Page to the Digital Age Volume 78, 2020 - Issue 1-4 <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/0361526X.2020.1744410>
- Kantabutra, S. (2020). Toward an organizational theory of sustainability vision. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 1125. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12031125>

- Kim, S., Raza, M., & Seidman, E. (2019). Improving 21st-century teaching skills: The key to effective 21st-century learners Research in Comparative and International Education 14(1):174549991982921 DOI:10.1177/1745499919829214
- Kluger, A., & Itzchakov, G. (2021). The power of listening at work. Annual Review of Organizational Psychology and Organizational Behavior, 9, 121-146. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-orgpsych-012420-091013>
- Larson, L. (2020). Leading teams in the digital age: four perspectives on technology and what they mean for leading teams. The Leadership Quarterly, 31(1)
- Leavy, P. (2022). Research Design: Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed Methods, Arts-Based, and Community-Based Participatory Research Approaches. Guilford Publications <https://www.selectedreads.com/what-is-quantitative-research-according-to-authors/>
- Loughran, J. (2021). Understanding self as a leader: emotional leadership and what it means for practice. Journal: Journal of Educational Administration and History, 53(2), 132. 10.1080/00220620.2020.1805418
- Lyssiotis, I. (2021) The Importance of Leadership Qualities in Students <https://blog.oeg.edu.au/the-importance-of-leadership-qualities-in-students>
- Mhunpiew N., & Asavisanu P. (2023). A Study of Teacher's Competency for Conducting a Professional Development Program at a Catholic School in Thailand Using the Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework <https://repository.au.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/1fe62c78-1f68-4379-82517717f1009c53/content>
- Maxwell, J. (2019). Leadershift: The 11 essential changes every leader must embrace. HarperCollins Leadership.
- Midha, G. (2021). School Leadership writ small: Meetings and school Principal Practice <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/17411432211058939>
- Molero, F., Mikulincer, M., Laguía, A., Moriano, J. A., & Shaver, P. R. (2019). The development and validation of the leader as security provider scale. Revista de Psicología del Trabajo y de las Organizaciones, 35(3), 183-193. <https://doi.org/10.5093/jwop2019a2>
- Morin, V. (2023) The Essence of Lifelong Learning Advocacy. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/essence-lifelong-learning-advocacy-jacquemorin-ed-d-nclsse>
- NCLSSE (2024). Teachers represent faculty and staff who are responsible for using a variety of instructional strategies to address individual students' strengths and needs, thereby ensuring each student has an opportunity to learn and succeed. Teachers | National Center on Safe Supportive Learning Environments (NCSSLE) (ed.gov)
- Nurlina N., Widayatsih T., & Lestari N, D. (2023). The Effect of Job Satisfaction and Motivation on the Organizational Commitment <https://doi.org/10.31851/jmksp.v8i1.10029>
- Owusu, B. (2022). Impact of Professional Development Programmes on Teachers' Knowledge and Academic Performance of Senior High School Students in Ghana. European Journal of Education and Pedagogy, 3(2), 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.24018/ejedu.2022.3.2.276>
- Ozgenel, M. (2020). The role of charismatic leader in school culture. Eurasian Journal of Educational Research, 20(86), 85-114.
- Pambuka, S. P. (2022). What makes a leader (diamond) is character. SA Pharmaceutical Journal, 89(2).
- Persaud, C. (2023) 25 Effective Instructional Strategies for Educators. 25 Effective Instructional Strategies for Educators | Top Hat

- Rajab, M. (2021). Literature review factors affecting leadership: quality of work, work effectiveness, and work communication. *Dinasti Publisher*, 2(2), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.38035/dijefa.v2i2>
- Rice, D.B., & Reed, N. (2022). Supervisor emotional exhaustion and goal-focused leader behavior: the roles of supervisor bottom-line mentality and conscientiousness. *Current Psychology*, 41(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-021-01349-8>
- Robb, L. (2020) The Crucial Role of Educational Leadership in Shaping the Future <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/crucial-role-educational-leadership-shaping-future>
- Rowinski, M. (2023). Leadership - Problem-Solving Skills. *Leadership – Problem Solving Skills* www.linkedin.com
- Sarwar, U., Tariq, R., & Yong, Q. (2022). Principals' leadership styles and its impact on teachers' performance at college level Volume 13 - 2022 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.919693>
- Simkus, J. (2023). Stratified Random Sampling: Definition, Method & Examples <https://www.simplypsychology.org/stratified-random-sampling.html>
- Singh, G. (2024). Educational Leadership and Professional Learning in Teacher Education: An Indian Perspective, *Educational Administration: Theory And Practice*, 30(4), 1871-1877, Doi: 10.53555/kuey.v30i4.1774
- SEAMEO INNOTECH (2020). Southeast Asia Teachers Competency Framework (SEA-TCF). https://www.seameo-innotech.org/portfolio_page/sea-tcf/
- Shidiq., G., Promkaew, S., & Faikhamta, C. (2022). Trends of competencies in teacher education from 2015 to 2020: A Systematic Review Analysis. *Kasetsart Journal of Social Sciences* 43(1):257-264 DOI: 10.34044/j.kjss.2022.43.1.35
- Smith, S., Strokes, P., Wen, J., & Yu, M. (2022). Building-up resilience and being effective leaders in the workplace: a systematic review and synthesis model. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 43(7), 1098-1117. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-09-2021-0437>
- Sulaiman, J., & Ismail, S. (2020). Teacher Competence and 21st Century Skills in Transformation Schools 2025 (TS25) *Universal Journal of Educational Research* Vol. 8(8), pp. 3536 - 3544 [10.13189/ujer.2020.080829](https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080829)
- Subedi, D. (2023), Efforts of Head Teachers In Leading And Managing Public School Through Developing Projects And Programmes | Request PDF (researchgate.net) P.32
- Trivissono, M. (2020). A passion for leadership: three studies. 1-24. *The Leadership of Innovation* (2023). *Innovation Leadership in 2023 The Leadership of Innovation* (2023) - Google Search
- UNESCO (2022). Teacher content knowledge. *Teacher content knowledge - IIEP Policy Toolbox*. www.unesco.org
- Utomo W., Udin, U., & Haryono, S. (2022). Visionary Leadership and Employee Quality in the Public Service Sector [10.33094/ijaefa.v12i2.542](https://doi.org/10.33094/ijaefa.v12i2.542)
- Vannier, D. (2023). Leading With Generosity. *Leading With Generosity* www.linkedin.com
- Vasquez, J. (2022). Principal Skills: Top 15 Every Principal Should Have *Principal Skills: Top 15 Every Principal Should Have* | Education Advanced, Inc.
- Villirilli, G. (2021). The importance of being an ethical leader and how to become one P. 12 *The Importance of Being an Ethical Leader and How to Become One* www.betterup.com
- Yalcinkaya, S., Dagli, G., Altınay, F., Altınay, Z., & Kalkan, Ü. (2021). The effect of leadership styles and initiative behaviors of school principals on teacher motivation. *Sustainability*, 13, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052711>
- Yazon, A., Callo, E., & Buenvenida, L. (2019) *Learning Guide in Methods of Research*. Wise,man's Books Trading Inc. Philippine Copyright, 2019

Žvinklys, A. (2024). Leadership Competency and Why It Matters.
<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/leadership-competency-why-matters-aivaras-%C5%BEvinklys-2bjrfP>